

Setting up the ENVI-met digital tool to evaluate climatic conditions at an urban scale: a case study of Djelfa, Algeria

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Key words:

ENVI-met model, green space, simulation, thermal comfort, urban heat stress, urban microclimate, urban planning, urbanized areas

ABSTRACT

Urbanization has radically transformed natural landscapes, giving rise to complex urban environments worldwide. This transformation poses unique challenges in terms of climatic conditions. We emphasize the crucial importance of understanding urban microclimates shaped by geographical, architectural and human factors, requiring meticulous management for sustainable urban planning. These multifaceted factors interact to produce spatial variations in solar exposure, temperature and wind conditions, leading to distinct microclimatic pockets within cities. This underlines the imperative need for sustainable urban planning and design that takes account of their impact. Our field survey is located in Djelfa, Algeria, featuring a semi-arid to arid climate with continental influences. This article presents a methodology involving a detailed morphological analysis of the urban fabric, focusing on its structure, vegetation cover and spatial characteristics. It describes the use of ENVI-met, a powerful microclimate simulation tool offering a complete three-dimensional modeling system that integrates various urban elements, including buildings, streets and green spaces. Our spatial considerations guarantee model accuracy, with a rigorous geometry validation process maintaining model fidelity. The tool produces invaluable output data, including air temperature, relative humidity and thermal comfort indices. This paper emphasizes on the application of the model in Djelfa, Algeria, highlighting its potential in evaluating thermal condition in urban environments. The results of our study highlight significant temperature and humidity disparities between urbanized and green areas in the survey area, with temperature differences of up to 6°C during the day. Urbanized areas consistently have higher air temperatures and lower humidity levels, particularly during the day. Conversely, green spaces, including gardens and tree-lined areas, exhibit lower temperatures and higher humidity levels, offering valuable respite from heat stress. The use of the Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) index allows us to assess thermal comfort, revealing variations in heat stress levels across the urban landscape. This research highlights the crucial importance of integrating green infrastructure into urban planning to improve thermal comfort and livability in cities. Furthermore, our study reveals the value of advanced tools like ENVI-met in understanding urban microclimates and provides valuable information for sustainable urban development and climate adaptation strategies.

Article processing

Submitted: 05 October 2023

Accepted: 22 November 2023

Published: 15 December 2023

Academic editor: Malte Hinsch

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1. Introduction

Urbanization is a global phenomenon that has brought unprecedented changes to the landscape of the planet, transforming vast expanses of natural terrain into complex networks of concrete and asphalt (Antrop 2004; Golubiewski and Wessman 2010). As much as urban environments offer opportunities and conveniences, they also pose unique challenges, particularly in the areas of microclimate and thermal comfort (Fotopoulou 2016). Local climatic conditions in cities often referred to as urban microclimates, resulting from the complex interactions between geographical, architectural, and human characteristics specific to urban environments. It is distinguished from regional or global climate by the presence of

several factors that combine to create specific atmospheric conditions in restricted spaces (Dimoudi et al. 2013).

Understanding the importance of these factors affecting urban climate and managing them effectively is at the heart of sustainable urban planning, which results in the creation of comfortable, livable living spaces for city dwellers. Several scientific research investigated this complex area, revealing the key parameters that govern the urban microclimate. Factors such as urban morphology (Coutts et al. 2007; Kaloustian and Bechtel 2016; Li et al. 2020; Lan et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2023), building materials (Kakoniti et al. 2016), topography (Oke 1982), surface color (Akbari 2009; Oleson et al. 2010), vegetation (Pérez et al. 2011; Soydan 2020), water bodies, and human activities (Min et al. 2019).

For instance, a study conducted by Lan et al. (2022) revealed that the arrangement and height of buildings could determine the amount of sunlight reaching different areas of the city throughout the day. Tall buildings and narrow streets may create shaded areas, while open spaces and boulevards receive more direct sunlight. This spatial variation in solar exposure leads to temperature differences across the city, affecting the local microclimate. Another study has been carried out by Coutts et al. (2007), showed that the shape and layout of the city create microclimatic pockets with distinct variations in temperature and wind conditions. Areas with higher building densities may experience increased heat retention and reduced air movement, resulting in warmer microclimates (Li et al. 2020). In contrast, open green spaces can provide relief from the heat and offer more favorable microclimatic conditions.

A study conducted by Soydan (2020) in Nigde, Turkey, found using correlation analysis that there was a significant difference in land surface temperature (LST) values between green and impervious surfaces. Impervious surfaces contribute to the formation of urban heat islands (UHI), while green surfaces have a cooling effect. It is therefore essential to increase the number of green surfaces in cities to improve urban quality of life. Beyond the cooling effect attributed to vegetation evapotranspiration, there is a study by Pérez et al. (2011) that confirms that vegetation assumes the role of a wind barrier when configured as a green screen. This confirms that this aspect of vegetation functions contributes to the complex interplay of microclimatic factors, further reinforcing the multifunctional aspect of the impact of urban vegetation.

The study by Ramyar et al. (2021) offers an illuminating insight into the importance of green infrastructure planning as a strategy for regulating urban microclimates and addressing the challenges of climate change. It highlights the need for interdisciplinary collaboration to integrate these concepts into urban planning practice and proposes a transdisciplinary approach to adaptively planning urban green infrastructure, with a view to promoting urban resilience and improving urban quality of life. Also, Gill et al. (2007) studied the same issue of adapting cities to climate change by focusing on the role of green infrastructure previously.

Among the various tools available for studying urban microclimates and thermal condition, the ENVI-met model has emerged as the most common and accurate dynamic numerical tool (Tsoka et al. 2018). This is a holistic, three-dimensional modeling system based on the fundamental laws of fluid dynamics and thermal dynamics (Bruse 1999). Developed to analyze micro-scale thermal interactions occurring in urban environments (Ouyang et al. 2022). It enables researchers and urban planners to simulate, analyze, and understand the intricate climatic dynamics within urban areas, providing valuable insights for sustainable urban development. This paper focuses on the application of the ENVI-met model in evaluating climatic conditions on an urban scale, with a specific emphasis on the Beautiful Shadow District (BSD) in Djelfa, Algeria.

ENVI-met has been employed as a vital tool in various research contexts and has garnered extensive validation. Multiple studies serve as evidence of its reliability and versatility. For instance, the research conducted by Alsaad et al. (2022) on the campus of Bauhaus-University Weimar in Weimar, Germany, as first stage of this research, measurements insitu were recorded to validate the ENVI-met simulation tool, simulations were then carried out using meteorological data, with the aim of studying the accuracy of the model. They calibrated the results, finding that this simulation tool is highly reliable and accurate for use in the further phase of their investigation.

Moreover, the work of Yang et al. (2013) emphasized its potential in the assessment and predict the microclimate as a function of different variables with good accuracy. Additionally, the research conducted by Bruse and Fleer (1998) describes the ENVI-met model, which simulates micro-scale interactions between surfaces, vegetation and the atmosphere. ENVI-met can be used to analyze the effects of small-scale changes in urban design on microclimate under different mesoscale conditions.

In summary, this study leverages the ENVI-met model to comprehensively investigate urban microclimates, emphasizing its capabilities encompassing the modeling of complex urban structures, including buildings, streets, green spaces, and more; by simulating these intricate urban environments, ENVI-met allows for a detailed examination of thermal comfort, air quality, and other climatic aspects. The results contribute valuable insights for urban design, vegetation planning, and climate change adaptation strategies.

2. Material and methods

2.1. The study area

The province of Djelfa is located on the high plateaux in the central part of northern Algeria, beyond the southern foothills of the northern Tellian Atlas, whose provincial capital of the same name lies 300 km south of the capital Algiers. It lies between 2° and 5° east longitude and between 33° and 35° north latitude (Derradji 2008; PDAU 2014).

It occupies a strategic position right in the center of the country and is characterized by its vast steppes territories (Boudiaf-Naitkaci et al. 2012), which contain a wealth of forest of over 214,000 ha of pine trees, constituting a distinct transition zone between the northern and southern climates at the gateway to the Sahara (Guit and Nedjimi 2020). Sharing its borders with Medea and Tissemsilt to the North, Msila, Ouled Djellal, and El Mghair to the East, Ouargla and Ghardaia to the South, and Laghouat and Tiaret to the West (Derradji 2008) (Fig. 1).

The relief of Djelfa province is characterized by the succession of four distinct zones from the north to the south of its territory. The highest point lies to the east of the Benyagoub settlement in the Daïra of Charef, at an altitude of 1,613 m, while the lowest point is in the extreme south of the Wilaya, at an altitude of 150 m. The main town of the commune lies at an altitude of 1,140 m (Derradji 2008).

2.1.1. City climate data

Djelfa, Algeria features a semi-arid to arid climate according to the Köppen BSk climate classification (Lohmann et al. 1993), with continental influences. The central and northern parts of the province have a semi-arid climate, while the southern part has an arid climate. The capital of the province of Djelfa, is located in the northern part, with a semi-arid climate, with hot, dry summers and cool, dry winters (Guit and Nedjimi 2020).

Figure 1. Location of study area, Djelfa, Algeria (d-maps 2020).

2.1.2. Air temperature

Annual temperatures in Djelfa vary considerably, with a wide range of variation throughout the year (Fig. 2). It records an average maximum temperature of 33.5°C (92.3°F) in July, and an average minimum temperature of 0.5°C (32.9°F) in January (NOAA 2019).

2.1.3. Precipitation

Djelfa is located in the central part of the province, which receives the most precipitation due to its high altitudes, with an average of 250 to 300 mm/y June and July were less rainy despite increased humidity (Fig. 3), with respectively 13 mm and 8 mm of precipitation over 6.1 to 6 days (NOAA 2019).

Figure 2. Yearly average air temperature, Djelfa, Algeria. Based on data from (NOAA 2019).

Figure 3. Yearly average air temperature, Djelfa, Algeria. Based on data from (NOAA 2019).

Table 1. Humidity levels (1990 to 2011), Djelfa, Algeria (NOAA 2019).

Months	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	Mai	Jun.	Jul.	Aug.	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
RH (%)	76.66	73.08	66.22	59.88	54.32	44.58	34.7	37.91	55.74	66.19	72.62	78.49

Relative humidity in Djelfa changes throughout the year. Relative humidity is normally lower, at 35-45%, during the hottest months, from June through August. However, relative humidity can reach above 80% in the winter months, particularly December and January, due to the lower capacity of fresh air to retain moisture. The table below shows the humidity values for Djelfa between 1990 and 2011.

2.1.4. Umbrothermal diagram by Bagnouls and Gausson

The Bagnouls and Gausson umbrothermal diagram (1953) provides a climatic classification based on mean annual temperature and precipitation (Lindquist and Hammel 1998). Over the course of the year, the umbrothermal diagram for the city of Djelfa reveals a dry season extending from May to mid-September, as demonstrated in Fig. 4 (Nesrine et al. 2022).

2.1.5. Location of field survey

The beautiful shadow district in the center of the city is the area chosen for the evaluation of the effect of vegetation on microclimate and thermal comfort (Fig. 5). It has a total area of 66,816 m². It features a range of urban forms, with building reach up to 12 m. It is characterized by a densely built-up environment. Vegetation takes a variety of forms, including squares, lines of trees and Garden.

2.1.6. Morphological analysis of the site

In our quest for a comprehensive morphological analysis of the field survey “Beautiful Shadow District”, a historic neighborhood within the city of Djelfa, we delve deeper into its origins, which systematically date back to the colonial period (PDAU 2014). It

Figure 4. The Bagnouls and Gausson umbrothermal diagram for Djelfa. Based on data from (NOAA 2019).

Figure 5. Location of field survey, the Beautiful shadow district, Djelfa (Modified from Google Maps ©2019).

was built according to a certain principle of urban composition, characterized by a complex urban fabric including a compact built environment presenting a variety of forms and activities enlivened with a highly vegetated open space. This interaction between the built environment and green spaces of the Beautiful Shadow District enriches the urban landscape, providing a natural space for the neighborhood and the city as a whole.

The built fabric of the district consists mainly of residential buildings, houses and villas, with a few public buildings such as a police station, a training center and a museum annexed to the Garden of Liberty. These buildings are characterized by their relatively low height, with most being one to three stories tall, although some reaching four or five floors. Their heights range from three to twelve

meters. Verticality is present in the skyline of the district, with building heights ranging from three to twelve meters. The road network is a mix of narrow streets and wide boulevards. The narrow streets are lined with buildings, while the wide boulevards give a feeling of openness and airiness. The road network is well served, providing easy access to all parts of the district.

Our in-depth morphological analysis enables us to collect a wide range of fundamental input data. Among these are details such as architectural patterns, building materials, vegetation structure and the road network. This data forms the indispensable basis on which we build holistic models more realistic a cornerstone of our research efforts, driving our evaluation process, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Morphological analysis of the study area, Djelfa (Modified from Google Maps ©2019).

2.1.7. Vegetation cover in the survey area

With its rich vegetation, charming gardens, pleasant squares and picturesque tree-lined avenues, the BSD stands out as the most verdant part of Djelfa city, contrasting with the galloping urban sprawl that surrounds it. Among these elements, trees hold an irreplaceable role within the urban landscape of this historic urban fabric, significantly improving the quality of life of the inhabitants of the city, offering essential benefits such as shade and a refreshing atmosphere.

In addition, the green public spaces within the district hold immense significance and contribute substantially to its unique character. These areas serve multiple purposes, serving as places for recreation, social gatherings, and community events. At the heart of our neighborhood is the magnificent “Garden of liberty” as shown the Fig. 7, a vast public park adorned with a rich variety of trees, vibrant flowers and elegant fountains. This garden has become a much-loved destination for residents and visitors alike, playing a key role in shaping the unique identity and ambience of the BSD.

One of the striking features of the study area is its remarkable plant biodiversity. It encompasses a wide range of plant typologies, including those introduced more recently, reflecting the richness of the vegetation cover in the city. There are various plant and tree species that are exceptionally well adapted to urban landscaping and local climatic conditions.

Figure 7. Garden of Liberty, Djelfa. **A** view from outside the garden, **B** view from inside the garden.

2.1.8. Reference weather station

Our reference meteorological station, the Djelfa meteorological station, is strategically located in the district of July 5th, about 4 km from our study area, as shown in Fig. 8. This station is supervised and operated by the National Centre for Meteorology (CNM) of Algeria. This station is equipped with a set of advanced instruments

designed to capture a full range of meteorological conditions. These instruments include sensors to measure temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed and direction, precipitation amount and snow depth. The data obtained from this local weather station is an essential reference point for our research.

Figure 8. Reference weather station, the meteorological station of Djelfa (Modified from Google Maps ©2019).

2.2. Methodology

In this study, our approach was to apply the ENVI-met digital tool to comprehensively assess climatic conditions on an urban scale (Matviienko 2019; Noirault et al. 2020; EnviMet). Our selected study area is the beautiful shadow neighborhood in Djelfa, Algeria, chosen for its unique urban characteristics and the relevance of our research objectives to this specific location.

Fig. 9, which we have included for clarity, illustrates the methodically constructed study framework. Within this framework, we have intricately detailed the sequential steps and distinct phases that guided our research process. In doing so, we aimed to provide an overview of our methodological approach, which encompasses data collection, model implementation, simulation processes and a strong analytical strategy. These steps collectively underlie the foundations of our research, ensuring a comprehensive and systematic exploration of urban climatic conditions in our study area. Fig. 9 is also a schematic overview of the ENVI-met model (Maleki et al. 2014; Noirault et al. 2020; Guerri et al. 2023), showing the flow of data through the model, from the input data to the output data.

2.2.1. Using ENVI-met tool for microclimate simulation

ENVI-met is an accurate tool for simulating and analyzing urban climates on a micro-scale (Ambrosini et al. 2014; Dursun and Yavaş 2018). Its process is complex and involves a number of steps. From the initial input data, which includes a wide range of information on the topography of the study area, buildings, vegetation, soils, etc. (Roth and Lim 2017), to the configuration file that defines the simulation parameters, ENVI-met meticulously prepares for its main task: the simulation engine.

Figure 9. Conceptual framework of the research.

To ensure the utmost accuracy in our simulations, we strictly adhered to specific spatial considerations. Horizontally, we ensured that the distance between buildings and model boundaries was zero or at least equivalent to the height of the building closest to the boundary (Salvati and Kolokotroni 2019). In terms of vertical spacing, we were careful to maintain a substantial buffer between the highest point of the buildings or the digital elevation model (DEM) borders. Generally, this distance is at least equal to the highest element of the model, providing around four to eight cells of free space along each boundary (Guerri et al. 2023). This strict adherence to spatial constraints has enabled us to maintain the quality of our models (the table below lists the various input settings used to create our model and run the simulation).

In addition, our goal of maintaining model accuracy was reinforced by a rigorous geometry validation process, as also indicated above. This last step served as a crucial quality assurance check to ensure that the structure of our model accurately reflected the actual conditions of our case study. In summary, our approach to creating three-dimensional models within the ENVI-met suite has been characterized by accuracy, fidelity and a firm commitment to reproducing the details of urban environments.

After creating the 3D model, we used ENVI-guide to run a simulation using the various parameters shown in Table 2. The simulation commenced at 7:00 AM and concluded at 10:00 PM on July 29, 2019, which was among the hottest days of the summer. For the meteorological boundary conditions, we employed a simple forcing approach. This involved defining various parameters based on the average meteorological data recorded by reference weather station (Salvati and Kolokotroni 2019).

2.2.2. The outputs of ENVI-met tool

ENVI-met is a numerical simulation tool play essential role, generating a series of output data used to study external thermal conditions. We are using an advanced ENVI-met Biomet post-processing tool to extract valuable information from the simulation data required for our study (Tsoka et al. 2018; Alves et al. 2022). It includes several of critical meteorological parameters such as air temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, specific humidity, etc. As well as five types of thermal comfort indices, including The Predicted Mean Vote (PMV), which is widely recognized in thermal comfort assessment and recommended by standards

such as ISO 7730 (2004) and ASHRAE (2020). The Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied (PPD), calculated based on PMV index, providing insights into occupants dissatisfaction likelihood. The Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET), acknowledged as one of the most suitable indices for urban thermal comfort assessment by Höppe (1999); and The Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), developed from the Fiala (2012) model and one of the

most advanced thermophysiological models available the last one. The Standard effective temperature (SET) is a widely used index for assessing thermal comfort. It was developed based on a two-node model that can reflect the human body thermal regulation process (Ji et al. 2022). All these indices provide a complete range of tools for assessing and improving thermal comfort in a variety of environments.

Table 2. Input data and initial settings for modelling and simulation by ENVI-met tool.

Model location			
Name of location		Djelfa, Algeria	
Position	Latitude (°)	34,68°	
	Longitude (°)	3,26°	
Model geometry			
Domaine size		348 m x 192 m	
Model dimension		X-Grids = 190	Y-Grids = 108 Z-Grids = 30
Size of Grid cell		$d_x = 2$	$d_y = 2$ $d_z = 1$
Model rotation out of grid north		14 °	
Height of 3D model TOP		30 m	
Highest point building + DFM		30 m	
Difference model top to highest point		18 m > h_{max}	($h_{max} = 12$ m)
Distance buildings to model border		6-9 Grids	(4-8)
Simulation setting			
Start Date		19 July 2019	
Star time		07:00	
Total simulation time (h)		15 hours	
Air temperature (°C)		24-hour cycle / CSV data	
Relative humidity (%)		24-hour cycle / CSV data	
Wind speed (m/s)		1.46	
Wind direction (°)		(N-O) 315	
Roughness length (m)		0.1	

3. Results and Discussion

In this research, we carried out an examination of climatic conditions in the urban landscape of the city of Djelfa “beautiful shadow district” during the summer season. Our main objective was to assess the thermal conditions and outdoor thermal comfort experienced by residents, using the ENVI-met simulation tool. Fig. 10 illustrates the 3D numerical model of the study area digitalized by the Spaces tool in the ENVI-met suite.

Our data collection extended over a fifteen-hour period on a typical day, one of the hottest of the year. We carefully quantified and registered temperature variations on an hourly basis, maintaining a constant height of 1.5 m above the ground. This height corresponded to a predefined position of the viewing plane.

Following a comprehensive review of all the data outputs for each hour of the day, we carefully identified and selected the most significant time points for in-depth analysis. Specifically, we pinpointed three pivotal moments of the daytime: 08:00, 12:00, and 16:00. During these selected hours, we delved into an examination of meteorological variables, concentrating on two key parameters: air temperature and relative humidity. These variables play a crucial role in shaping the microclimatic conditions within the urban fabric of Djelfa city during the summer season.

During all the hour of day have been simulated, the air temperature ranged between 25.31°C to 42.02°C, corresponding to relative humidity ranged between 8.59% and 49.51%. According to Figs. 11, 12, the air temperature at 08:00 ranged from 23.93°C and 29.61°C, relative humidity ranged between 21.11% and 49.51%.

Figure 10. ENVI-met Model of the study area.

08:00 29.07.2019

x/y Cut at k=5 (z=1.5000 m)

Air temperature

Min: 23.93 °C
Max: 29.61 °C

Figure 11. Air temperature of the study area at 08:00.

08:00 29.07.2019

x/y Cut at k=5 (z=1.5000 m)

Relative Humidity

Min: 21.11 %
Max: 49.51 %

SC01

Figure 12. Relative humidity of the study area at 08:00.

The temperature distribution on the Fig. 12 shows some interesting features. Firstly, temperatures are generally higher in the central and northern parts of the zone, and lower in the remaining parts. This is clearly due to the fact that the central and northern parts of the zone are more urbanized, which can lead to higher temperatures “heat stress zone” (Helbling and Meierrieks 2023).

In addition, the temperature map shows that the area is relatively cooler in the green areas and open spaces of the urban fabric, i.e. gardens (Zhang et al. 2022). The lowest air temperature in these areas is less than 23.93°C. The distribution of relative humidity is similar to that of temperatures, but vice versa, since the highest humidity values are recorded in planted areas, reaching 49.51%, which is the maximum value for a whole day. The relative humidity is influenced by the presence of vegetation, which can generate water vapor and increase the relative humidity in the surrounding air (Thomson 1964; Meili et al. 2021; Chen et al. 2023).

As illustrated by Fig. 13, at noon, the values of air temperature ranged between 33.06°C and 39.19°C, with a difference of up to

6.13°C. The distribution of air temperature is similar as in the morning, with some variations. For example, we recorded a relatively lower air temperature in the part dotted by trees in the urbanized zone. This is likely due to the fact that trees provide shade and release water vapor, which can help to cool the air (Aram et al. 2019). At the same time, the highest air temperature value, over 39°C, is recorded in the densest part of the urbanized area.

In addition, relative humidity ranged from 9.72% to 25.25% (Fig. 14), lower overall than in the morning. With a difference of 15.53% less than in the morning, when 28.4% was recorded between the urbanized area and the green space.

In the evening at 16:00, as shown in Figs. 15, 16, we observe that the difference between the maximum and minimum values is lower for both air temperature and relative humidity, at 4.17°C and 6.57%, respectively. As we can see, the heat stress zone is still mainly located in dense urban areas. On the other hand, gardens and detached houses with private gardens benefit from lower air temperatures.

Figure 13. Air temperature of the study area at 12:00.

Figure 14. Relative humidity of the study area at 12:00.

12:00 29.07.2019

x/y Cut at k=5 (z=1.5000 m)

Air temperature

- below 33.70 °C
- 33.70 to 34.30 °C
- 34.30 to 34.90 °C
- 34.90 to 35.50 °C
- 35.50 to 36.10 °C
- 36.10 to 36.70 °C
- 36.70 to 37.30 °C
- 37.30 to 37.90 °C
- 37.90 to 38.50 °C
- above 38.50 °C

Min: 33.06 °C
Max: 39.19 °C

12:00 29.07.2019

x/y Cut at k=5 (z=1.5000 m)

Relative Humidity

- below 11.28 %
- 11.28 to 12.83 %
- 12.83 to 14.38 %
- 14.38 to 15.93 %
- 15.93 to 17.49 %
- 17.49 to 19.04 %
- 19.04 to 20.59 %
- 20.59 to 22.15 %
- 22.15 to 23.70 %
- above 23.70 %

Min: 9.72 %
Max: 25.25 %

SC01

Going beyond the simplicity of traditional temperature measurements by exploring the complex interactions between climatic conditions and human responses, through the integration of meteorological, thermophysiological parameters, clothing, and human activities (Höppe 1999). We chose the PET index for assessing thermal comfort in urban areas, as it is one of the most appropriate and widely used indices in recent research (Zhang et al. 2023).

According to Figs. 17–19, the PET outdoor thermal comfort index values fluctuate between 22°C and 32°C at 08:00. In line with the different categories defined by Höppe (1999), no thermal stress is generally observed at the start of the day, although slight thermal stress does occur, particularly in streets and spaces exposed to direct sunlight.

At noon, the PET ranged between 36.74°C and 43.80°C, with level of heat stress occurs between moderate, strong and extreme. While at 16:00, the PET ranged between 39.80°C and 47.66°C with level of

heat stress strong or extreme. Typically, the heat stress is cooler in the green space and near space planted by trees. These findings suggest that people should be aware of the risks of heat stress, particularly during the hottest part of the day and in areas exposed to direct sunlight.

Moreover, the outcomes of this research open avenues for prospective actions aimed at enhancing the quality of outdoor conditions in urbanized areas. The advanced numerical model developed in this study serves as a valuable tool for envisioning and implementing transformative strategies. Through its ability to simulate complex interactions within urban environments, is instrumental in creating scenarios that assess the potential effects of such factors as increased greenery on microclimates. By quantifying the expected changes in air temperature, humidity, and overall thermal comfort, policymakers can make informed decisions based on evidence that promote more comfortable and resilient urban environments.

Figure 15. Air temperature of the study area at 16:00.

Figure 16. Relative humidity of the study area at 16:00.

Figure 17. The physiological equivalent temperature values of the study area at 08:00.

Figure 18. The physiological equivalent temperature values of the study area at 12:00.

Figure 19. The physiological equivalent temperature values of the study area at 16:00.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research carried out in Djelfa, Algeria, using the ENVI-met digital tool, offers valuable insights into the complex interplay of climatic conditions in urban environments during the summer season. The study focused on assessing thermal conditions and outdoor thermal comfort for residents, with a particular emphasis on air temperature and relative humidity.

The research revealed significant variations in air temperature and relative humidity throughout the day, with distinct patterns observed at different times. Notably, the built parts of the urban area experienced higher temperatures, leading to localized heat stress. This is likely due to a number of factors, including the presence of buildings, pavement, and other impervious surfaces in the urbanized area, which absorb and retain heat. Conversely, green spaces and areas with vegetation showed lower temperatures and higher relative humidity, highlighting the cooling effect of vegetation in urban environments.

The application of the PET index provided a comprehensive understanding of thermal comfort. The results indicated that residents might experience thermal stress, ranging from moderate to extreme, during the hottest parts of the day, especially in urbanized zones exposed to direct sunlight. However, the presence of green spaces, such as gardens and tree-lined areas, offered relief from heat stress and contributed to more comfortable microclimatic conditions.

These findings underscore the importance of urban planning and design decisions that prioritize green spaces and vegetation to mitigate heat stress and improve the quality of life for urban residents. The study demonstrates the value of advanced tools like ENVI-met in assessing and understanding urban microclimates, which can inform sustainable urban development and climate adaptation strategies. Looking ahead, this research suggests potential future steps that involve exploring strategies to restructure urbanized areas and improve outdoor conditions. The developed numerical model could be leveraged to create scenarios, such as increasing green infrastructure in the study area, providing a tangible framework for informed decision-making in urban planning.

Overall, this study not only contributes to the understanding of urban microclimates but also provides a foundation for future research and practical applications in sustainable urban planning and climate adaptation strategies.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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